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MANUFACTURING PROCESS AND PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PEEK COMPOSITE MODEIFIED WITH MWNTS

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Outline

- Introduction
- Experiment and Result
- Team Work

1.Introduction

	PEI	PPS	PEEK	PEKK
Morphology	Amorphous	Semi-Crystalline	Semi-Crystalline	Semi-Crystalline
Chemical Structure	<chem>*c1ccc(cc1)C2=CC=CC=C2C3=CC=CC=C3C4=CC=CC=C4C5=CC=CC=C5C6=CC=CC=C6*</chem>	<chem>*c1ccc(cc1)S*</chem>	<chem>*c1ccc(cc1)Oc2ccc(cc2)Oc3ccc(cc3)C(=O)c4ccc(cc4)*</chem>	<chem>*c1ccc(cc1)C(=O)c2ccc(cc2)C(=O)c3ccc(cc3)C(=O)c4ccc(cc4)*</chem>
T _g (°C)	217	90	143	156
T _m (°C)	343	282	343	338
Processing Temperature (°C)	343	315~340	350~380	340
Working Temperature (°C)	170	180-240	250-260	260
Comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ High T_g ✓ Moderate Processing Temperature * Environmental Resistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Excellent Environmental Resistance ✓ Moderate Processing Temperature * Low T_g * Low Toughness * Poor Paint Adhesion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Extensive Database ✓ Excellent Environmental Resistance ✓ High Toughness * High Process Temperature * High Polymer Cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Excellent Environmental Resistance ✓ High Toughness ✓ Lower Process Temperature than PEEK ✓ Bonding and Painting * Difficult Dissolution * High Polymer Cost

1.Introduction

2. Experiment and Result

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2. Experiment

Interlaminar shear strength of composites

Flexural properties of composites

2. Experiment

The Mode-I fracture toughness of composites

- The Mode-I fracture toughness is evaluated by DCB test according to ASTM D5528

2. Experiment

- The agglomeration of MWNTs can lead to microdefects in the composites.

3. Team Work

Manufacture of CF/PEEK prepregs

CF/PEEK prepregs with 20cm width

Metallographic images of CF/PEEK prepregs with 35% (a, A) and 50% (b, B) fiber volume fraction

Creels

Fiber expanding

Tension control

Extruder

Infiltration system

Winding system

Manufacturing facility of CF/PEEK prepregs by co-extrusion

3. Team Work Optimized Impregnation Prediction Model of PEEK

Geometry of impregnation model: (a) previous model by other researchers, (b) simplified model for the impregnation of fiber bundles in manufacturing preregs

Hypothesis:

- PEEK resin is regarded as **Newton fluid**
- Fiber bundles are Consider as **oval shape**

Experimental verification

Degree of impregnation as a function of pressure: simulation (a) and experiments (b)

3. Team Work

Thank You for Your Attention

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